

Customers' Perception of Motives and Barriers to Organic Food Products in Haryana

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Abstract

Food is one of the basic needs of human beings throughout the world. In India, due to the increasing population continuously, the requirement for various types of foods has also increased over time. It has been observed from various reports that the food produced or supplied to the people of India is either contaminated/adulterated or has poor quality, affecting the health of the masses and giving birth to various types of health issues. Considering the situation, many farmers/organizations of farmers came forward with the idea of producing and supplying organic food items to combat the menace of poor food quality leading to health issues. The present paper aims to perceive consumers of organic food items towards various related aspects. The study is purely based on primary data collected through a questionnaire from the customers of Haryana, which were analyzed with appropriate statistical techniques.

Keywords: Sustainable Agriculture, Organic Food Products, Healthy, Perception, Motives

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Introduction

Agriculture has a substantial impact on the environment, creating and being affected by environmental changes at the same time. It contributes considerably to water scarcity, pollution, deforestation, land degradation, and other processes. (Brown 2012). Global food system emissions in 2015 totaled 18 Gt CO₂ equivalent year, or 34% of all GHG emissions. Enormous contributions came from agriculture and land use/land-use change activities (71 percent). The remaining portion was generated by supply chain activities, including retail, fuel production, transportation, consumption, waste management, packaging, and industrial operations. (Crippa et al., 2021). It is necessary to implement sustainable agriculture techniques to tackle such grave concerns.

The goal of sustainable agriculture is to satisfy society's present food and clothing needs without endangering the ability of future generations to do the same. (sarep.ucdavis.edu). Agricultural systems may be able to maintain a growing population while adjusting to shifting environmental circumstances through the use of sustainable agriculture. In agriculture, "sustainability" refers to a comprehensive, long-term strategy for business on the farm that maximizes economic and environmental stability, equity, and health of the farm, business, and family (www.omafra.gov.on.ca). Numerous sustainable agriculture practices exist, and the most prevalent among them is "Organic Farming." The term "organic" is used on packaging to indicate that food or other agricultural products were produced in accordance with accepted practices. To improve resource cycling, ecological balance, and biodiversity protection, these solutions combine cultural, biological, and mechanical activities. (www.ams.usda.gov). Natural ingredients are used to create organic food, which is devoid of synthetic chemicals like antibiotics, herbicides, pesticides, and fertilizers (Gad Mohsen & Dacko, 2013). As a result, customers view organic food as healthy because it does not include any synthetic ingredients (Suprpto & Wijaya, 2012).

There is 1.5 percent of organic croplands. Market research company Ecovia Intelligence claims that in 2018, the worldwide market for organic food, for the first time, surpassed \$100 billion US (almost 97 billion euros). The largest market is the United States, with 40.6 billion euros, followed by Germany (10.9 billion euros) and France (9.1 billion euros). In 2018, 2.8 million organic farmers were identified. India continues to have the most producers (11,49,000), followed by Uganda (2,10,000) and Ethiopia (2,04,000) (www.globalagriculture.org).

Review of Literature

(Canavari & Olson, 2007) asserted that organic farming has always been a healthy approach to production adopted by some farmers worldwide. Consumers' attention to food safety and environmental issues has risen dramatically in recent decades due to their growing

concern for their health, the health of the environment, and global crises and emergencies. (Sangkumchaliang & Huang, 2012) analyzed the state of customers' opinions of organic foods in Northern Thailand. They surveyed a sample of 390 respondents from different locations in the country. According to the results, the major drivers of buying organic food items are hopes for a better and more sustainable production process. Compared to non-buyers, persons who purchase organic products are often older and more educated. The pricing of the products and customer confidence in their legitimacy are further problems. Consumer awareness, however, remains the biggest obstacle to boosting the market share of organic food items.

The increased prevalence of lifestyle problems, including heart conditions and depression, significantly impacts how modern consumers change. The requirement to buy organic food to enhance the quality of life will significantly impact corporate functions related to retail, distribution, and marketing (Rana & Paul, 2017).

(Dangi et al., 2020) reviewed previously conducted research on the characteristics that affect the purchase of organic food, paying particular attention to eco-labels, and determined the relative importance of these drivers. Based on time, region, and national economic status, an analysis of 91 research studies involving 1,54,072 consumers reporting from 2001 to 2020. The study concluded that personal factors like health concerns, environmental concerns, knowledge and awareness, eco-labels, price, and trust in organic food are the most important when purchasing organic food.

After surveying 110 respondents in rural Haryana (Kumar & Gulati, 2017) found that low level of income, irregular availability, high prices, limited variety, and lack of knowledge are the most significant barriers to purchasing organic products among consumers in rural Haryana.

(Pandey & Misra, 2016) analyzed the consumers' behavior towards organic food products and found out the reasons for not purchasing the organic products using percentage analysis. The study was conducted on 170 respondents selected through a convenient sampling method. Most consumers found that organic products are better in taste, quality, and health benefits; at the same time, consumers believed organic products to be expensive and scarce.

Based on data gathered from 240 respondents (120 consumers of organic food and 120 consumers of non-organic food) in Tamil Nadu's Tirupur district, (Krishnakumare & Niranjana, 2017) explored how customers behave when purchasing organic food goods. Chi-square analysis and multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) were used to analyze the data for the study. In addition to examining awareness, the study discovered a correlation

between demographic characteristics and awareness of organic food products. The study found that organic and non-organic food consumers differ based on gender, household income, education, and job status.

(Chattopadhyay & Khanzode, 2019) examined the awareness level of consumers regarding organic products in Bengaluru. The study comprises 105 respondents selected via the convenience sampling technique. The awareness level of consumers is measured on the basis of various demographic characteristics of respondents like age, income, gender, education etc. Bengaluru has the highest sales of organic food items and the most number of organic food stores, which are expanding at a pace of 35-40% annually.

To better understand the traits, viewpoints, and purchasing habits of various customer categories, (Gumber et al., 2021) studied 556 people. Through the use of exploratory factor analysis, they were able to isolate six elements, including those related to health, humanity, and the environment, trust and confidence, purchasing barriers, tradition and culture, fundamental knowledge, and social acceptance and status. Additionally, customers are divided into the following five groups: unconcerned, incognizant, critical, conservative, and congruent consumers.

(Khandelwal, 2022) studied the consumers' attitudes toward sustainable food, as well as customers' views of sustainable food and their preferences for organic food. The study also looked at consumer preferences and behaviors in quick-service restaurants and conscious efforts/actions to prevent food waste, which is crucial to food sustainability. The study's goal was to identify consumers' green values, their awareness of sustainable food options, their level of environmental concern, the factors that affect their food purchase decisions, and the obstacles to buying sustainable food. The study gathered data from 219 respondents using a structured questionnaire. It also highlights consumer preferences for packaging, their understanding of how sustainability affects food, and how they dispose of food waste.

Objective

1. To know the customers' perception of organic products' use and authenticity criteria.
2. To identify the motives and barriers to organic products.

Research Methodology

A predetermined questionnaire (Bryla, 2016) was modified and used after incorporating the pilot study's feedback. The questionnaire was built using google forms and sent to a convenient sample of 100 respondents via social media platforms, but only 82 responded. To minimize the difference in subjective understanding of respondents, the definition of organic products, i.e., food grown without using synthetic chemicals, is mentioned in the

questionnaire. The collected data is analyzed using simple percentage analysis.

Results and Discussions

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Particulars		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	33	40.2
	Male	49	59.8
Age of Respondent	21-40	69	84.1
	41-60	13	15.9
Level of Education	Upto 12th	3	3.7
	Graduate	14	17.1
	Post Graduate	50	61
	Ph.D.	15	19.2
Annual Income of Respondent	Up to 5 lacs	34	41.5
	500001-10 lacs	25	30.5
	above ten lacs	23	28
Consumption of organic products	Regularly	23	28
	Occasionally	43	52.2
	Rarely	16	19.5
Residence of Respondent	Urban	55	67.1
	Rural	27	32.9
Family type	Joint	40	48.8
	Nuclear	42	51.2
Food Habit	Vegetarian	75	91.5
	Non-vegetarian	7	8.5
	Vegan	0	0

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of organic food consumers (respondents). Almost 60 percent are males, and 40 percent are females. It shows that 84 percent of the consumers are 21-40 years old, while 16 percent are from the 41-60 age group. A meager 3.7 percent of the consumers studied up to 12th class, 17.1 percent have done their graduation, the majority of 61 percent are postgraduates, and 19.2 percent are Ph.D. holders. The majority of respondents (41.5 percent) have an annual income of less than ` Five lacs, 30.5 percent of respondents have an annual income between ` 500001 and ten lacs, and 28 percent with an annual income above ` ten lacs. The majority (52.2 percent) of the respondents occasionally consume organic products, 28per cent of the respondents are regular

consumers, and only 20 percent of the consumers have rarely consumed organic products. Out of the total respondents, 67 per cent lives in urban areas, and the remaining 33 per cent lives in rural areas. While 49 percent of consumers have joint families, 51 percent have nuclear families. The majority of the respondents (91.5 percent) are vegetarians, and only a few (8.5 percent) are non-vegetarians. No single consumer from the survey is a Vegan.

Table 2: Respondents' View Toward Organic and Conventional Food (total sample) (%)

Statements	Definitely Yes	Rather Yes	Don't Know	Rather Not	Definitely Not
It is expensive	45.1	39	6.1	6.1	3.7
It is healthier	89	9.8	1.2	-	-
It is more environmentally friendly	80.5	18.3	1.2	-	-
It arouses more trust	62.2	26.8	11	-	-
It has a better quality	70.7	24.4	4.9	-	-
It is governed by more stringent regulations.	42.7	36.6	14.6	4.9	1.2
It is produced more traditionally	36.6	36.6	20.7	4.9	1.2
It is tastier	36.6	41.5	14.6	6.1	1.2
It is more authentic	57.7	26.8	14.6	1.2	-
I advise its purchase to my family/friends	65.9	25.6	8.5	-	-
I accept its higher price	35.4	43.9	12.2	7.3	1.2
It looks better	40.2	29.3	23.2	6.1	1.2
Its advertising is adequate	25.6	34.1	23.2	4.9	12.2

Note: The figures in Table 2 represent the percent share out of the total sample.

The respondents were asked to compare organic and conventional food (Table 2). Forty-five percent of them think it is more expensive than conventional products, and an additional 2/5 rather share this opinion. Nearly all of the research participants assert that organic foods are healthier and more ecologically friendly than conventional ones. 95% of those surveyed think organic food is of greater quality than conventional food. Almost 70 percent of respondents found organic food tastier, traditional, and subject to strict controls. More than 80% of consumers thought it was more authentic than traditional food; therefore, they advised their friends and relatives to buy it. 1/3 of the respondents accepted the premium prices of organic products, and a further 2/5 rather shared this opinion. Only 1/4 of the consumers find the advertising of organic food products adequate, and a further 1/3

rather shared the same opinion, while almost 17 percent of consumers find the advertising inadequate. Consumers have perceived organic food products as more valued than their conventional counterparts (Suciu et al., 2019). The occasional organic consumers that were price sensitive opted for conventional plus products, while the price-insensitive consumers preferred organic products (Stolz et al., 2021).

Exhibit 1: Perception of Consumers Towards Characteristics of Organic Products

As shown in (Exhibit 1), the three most essential qualities of customers' perceptions of organic products are high quality (59.8%), environmental concern (63.4%), and healthiness (92.7%). Almost half of the consumers also emphasized 'origin from organic plantations.' Cooperation, typicity, and landscape ability are the least important characteristics. Consumer perceptions of the health and safety element are characterized by concerns about health and how the product is produced concerning animal welfare and environmental care (Ayuni & Rennie, 2012). A consumer's opinion of the product's safety, health, and environmental impact substantially impacted their decision to buy organic food (Wee et al., 2014).

Exhibit 2: Organic Food Authenticity Assessment Criteria

Here, the evaluation criteria for perceived organic product authenticity are mentioned. As shown in (Exhibit 2) the consumers are most dependent on natural taste (80.5 %), product quality (79.3 %), and certification (64.6 %), respectively, to authenticate organic food products. The least important criteria were the retailer, merchandising, packaging, scarcity, tourism, and brand name.

Exhibit 3: Organic Food Market- Barriers to Growth

Barriers to the development of the organic food market/ Why don't you buy organic products?

(select any 3)

82 responses

(Exhibit 3) shows the most significant barriers to the growth of organic food market, i.e., availability (74.4 %), price (70.7 %), and knowledge (46.3 %), respectively. 1/4 of the consumers also found marketing and substitutes to be significant barriers. The least effective barriers to the development of the organic food market were appearance (4.9 %), mistakes (6.1 %), taste (7.3 %), merchandising (7.3 %), and skepticism (9.8 %), respectively. According to (Buder et al., 2014), regular consumers of organic food listed price, a lack of availability, and product quality as their top three barriers to purchasing organic goods

Exhibit 4: Organic Food Selection Motives

Organic food selection motives

82 responses

As shown in (Exhibit 4), the consumers are motivated the most by healthiness (98.8 %), quality assurance (72 %), safety (61 %), vitamins (61 %), and taste (50 %) of organic products, respectively. 1/4th of the respondents felt motivated by the traditional recipe. Less than 5 percent of respondents considered traceability, proximity, advertising, retailer, nostalgia, fashion, smell, brand, price, curiosity, and pleasure as motivating factors to buy organic products. Somewhat respondents considered uniqueness, recommendation, animal welfare, local producers, and loyalty as motivating factors.

Managerial Implications

Despite organic food being considered healthful, consumers in the research area hesitate to purchase organic food due to a lack of confidence in its authenticity. Therefore, to increase consumer purchase intent, the organization that manufactures and sells organic food products must determine how to build customer trust. This study informs market participants about the best approaches to take in order to maximize the sales potential of organic food items among various customer groups. The study will also benefit policymakers by offering insightful information and assisting them in making the necessary efforts to promote organic food items.

Limitations of the Study

This study's application of its conceptual framework to just one product category-organic food-represents a drawback. The operationalization of the study in Haryana does not enable the results to be generalizable in other Indian states. The results of this study may not apply to other contexts because the spread and underlying factors influencing the adoption and rejection of organic food may vary depending on the region. The demographic variables of the study are not uniformly distributed. The sample size of the study is small.

Conclusion

The study attempts to understand the motives and barriers to purchase decisions of organic food products. Understanding how consumers view organic food products is critical because this will influence whether they intend to purchase and consume the goods. It will ultimately result in the actual behavior of buying the products. The study concluded that people are getting more and more knowledge about the benefits (healthy, natural, environmentally friendly, tasty, etc.) of organic food products as their education level increases. It also showed that consumers have a more positive outlook toward organic products and are more willing to pay higher prices for these products. The barriers to accepting organic food products can be removed by reducing prices and increasing product availability. Policymakers should include provisions for community-supported agriculture, contract agriculture, and farmers' markets to promote organic farming and goods. To make organic food more widely available, farmers/producers, retailers, marketers, policymakers, and consumers must work together.

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Webography

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What is Sustainable Agriculture? | Sustainable Agriculture Research & Education Program (ucdavis.edu)